

EXERCISES ON THE GEOMETRIC PHASE FOR SPIN 1 ¹

Geometric phase (Pancharatnam-Berry phase)

When the polarization state of light undergoes a series of unitary or hermitian operations and returns to its original state, the final state differs in an additional overall phase factor from the original one. It was pointed out by Pancharatnam that this phase difference is not only due to the dynamical phase from the accumulated path lengths but also involves a geometric phase [1]. Berry introduced the corresponding theory for the quantum mechanical state vector and rederived the Pancharatnam's geometric phase [2, 3]. If the cyclic path consists of only great circles, dynamical phase will not develop, and the geometric part increases by an amount $\pm\Omega/2$, where Ω is the solid angle that the geodesic closed path subtends on the Poincare sphere. \pm sign depends the sense of rotation of the cyclic path and it also depends on the choice of the left/right handedness.

In polarization optics unitary operations are employed by retarders and hermitian-projection operations by polarizers. Algebra of the polarization optics is isomorphic to the algebra of spin $\frac{1}{2}$ [4, 5]. That is why we have $\delta = \pm\Omega/2$, but for spin 1, $\delta = \pm\Omega$.

Eigenvectors of $\Sigma \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}$ for spin 1

Geometric phase (Pancharatnam-Berry phase) can be realized after a series of operations on the state vector. For spin 1 we have to use the eigenvectors of the hermitian operator $\Sigma \cdot \mathbf{n}$

$$\Sigma \cdot \mathbf{n} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -ic & is\phi \\ ic & 0 & -is\phi \\ -is\phi & is\phi & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $c = \cos \theta$, $s = \sin \theta$, $\phi = \cos \phi$, $\phi = \sin \phi$, $\mathbf{n} = (s\phi, s\phi, c)$ and $\Sigma = i(S_1, S_2, S_3)$

$$S_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad S_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad S_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$\Sigma \cdot \mathbf{n}$ is a traceless Hermitian matrix and it has 3 orthogonal eigenvectors corresponding to the eigenvalues ± 1 and 0.

$$\varphi_+ = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} -c\phi - i\phi \\ -c\phi + i\phi \\ s \end{pmatrix}, \quad \varphi_- = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} -c\phi + i\phi \\ -c\phi - i\phi \\ s \end{pmatrix}, \quad \varphi_0 = \begin{pmatrix} s\phi \\ s\phi \\ c \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

In the following examples we will use φ_- which corresponds to the left-helicity [10] and write $\varphi_- = \varphi$.

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Example 1. Geometric phase with unitary operations (rotations) on great circles on a sphere (no dynamical phase)

Let's consider the following successive rotations $A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C \rightarrow A$ on a sphere as depicted in Figure 1. A general rotation matrix that rotates φ about an axis \mathbf{n} by an angle α is given by

$$R(\mathbf{n}, \alpha) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \alpha + n_x^2(1 - \cos \alpha) & n_x n_y(1 - \cos \alpha) - n_z \sin \alpha & n_x n_z(1 - \cos \alpha) + n_y \sin \alpha \\ n_x n_y(1 - \cos \alpha) + n_z \sin \alpha & \cos \alpha + n_y^2(1 - \cos \alpha) & n_y n_z(1 - \cos \alpha) - n_x \sin \alpha \\ n_x n_z(1 - \cos \alpha) - n_y \sin \alpha & n_y n_z(1 - \cos \alpha) + n_x \sin \alpha & \cos \alpha + n_z^2(1 - \cos \alpha) \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Rotation matrices about x, y and z axis are

Figure 1: Cyclic unitary operations on great circles (no dynamical phase)

$$R_x(\alpha_x) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \alpha & -\sin \alpha \\ 0 & \sin \alpha & \cos \alpha \end{pmatrix}, \quad R_y(\alpha_y) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \alpha & 0 & \sin \alpha \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin \alpha & 0 & \cos \alpha \end{pmatrix}, \quad R_z(\alpha_z) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \alpha & -\sin \alpha & 0 \\ \sin \alpha & \cos \alpha & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

For successive rotations with $\alpha_x = \alpha_y = \alpha_z = 90^\circ$, as given in Figure 1, the combined rotation matrix R_T is

$$R_T = R_z(90^\circ)R_y(90^\circ)R_x(90^\circ) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

R_T acts on the helicity vector $\varphi = \varphi_A$ where $\theta = 90^\circ$, $\phi = 90^\circ$:

$$R_T \varphi_A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ -i \end{pmatrix} = -i \varphi_A \quad (7)$$

Therefore, the overall phase difference is $\delta = -90^\circ$ and it is equal to the area subtended by the closed path with a minus sign, $\delta = -\Omega$. Note that here the geometric phase is doubled as compared to the case with spinors ($\text{spin}\frac{1}{2}$).

In this example we have rotated the state vector along the great circles, therefore there was no dynamical phase involved. But in general, there will be a dynamical phase which should be taken into account. We have to subtract the dynamical phase from the total phase to obtain the net geometric phase. This situation is examined in the following example.

Example 2. Geometric phase with rotations involving dynamical phase

Figure 2: Unitary operations that involve dynamical phase)

In Figure 2 the closed path $A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C \rightarrow A$ is traversed by unitary operations (rotations), but now the path $A \rightarrow B$ is not a great circle, hence the state vector picks up a dynamical phase on this path.

Let's first calculate the total phase. At point A, $\theta = 60^\circ, \phi = 0^\circ$,

$$\varphi_A = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} \\ -i \\ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

We apply three successive rotations on φ_A , $R_T = R_y(60^\circ)R_x(60^\circ)R_z(90^\circ)$

$$R_z(90^\circ) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad R_x(60^\circ) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ 0 & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}, \quad R_y(60^\circ) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & 0 & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Hence,

$$R_T \varphi_A = \frac{-i}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} \\ -i \\ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \end{pmatrix} = -i \varphi_A \quad (10)$$

Therefore the total phase is $\delta_{total} = -90^\circ$. Now we calculate the dynamical phase on the path $A \rightarrow B$:

$$\delta_{dynamic} = \text{Im} \int_{\phi_A}^{\phi_B} \varphi^\dagger \frac{d}{d\phi} \varphi d\phi = -\text{Im} \int_{\phi_A}^{\phi_B} i \cos \theta d\phi = -\cos \theta (\phi_B - \phi_A) = -45^\circ \quad (11)$$

Magnitude of $\delta_{dynamic}$ is equal to the area $ABED$. Therefore the geometric phase is

$$\delta_{geo} = \delta_{total} - \delta_{dynamic} = -45^\circ \quad (12)$$

Magnitude of the geometric phase is equal to the area Ω of the cap portion subtended by the closed path. Minus sign is due to the counter-clockwise rotation and left handedness of the state vector:

$$\delta_{geo} = -\Omega \quad (13)$$

0.1 Geometric phase with hermitian (projection) operators

Figure 3: Projection operations

Consider three projection operations on the initial state φ_A as given in Figure 3. Projection operator does not induce dynamical phase on path $A \rightarrow B$, therefore we treat this path as a great circle and expect that the area subtended will turn out to be equal to the geometric phase.

The projection operator for the path $A \rightarrow B$ is $\varphi_B \varphi_B^\dagger$, for the path $B \rightarrow C$, $\varphi_C \varphi_C^\dagger$, and for the path $C \rightarrow A$, $\varphi_A \varphi_A^\dagger$. Since we want to find only the phase difference we can omit the normalization factors and write:

$$\delta_{geo} = \arg[\varphi_A^\dagger (\varphi_A \varphi_A^\dagger) (\varphi_C \varphi_C^\dagger) (\varphi_B \varphi_B^\dagger) \varphi_A] \quad (14)$$

In the given example

$$\varphi_A = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} \\ -i \\ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \varphi_B = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} i \\ -\frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \varphi_C = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} -1 \\ -i \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (15)$$

After calculations

$$\tan \delta_{geo} = -0.75, \quad \text{hence} \quad \delta_{geo} = -36.8699^\circ \quad (16)$$

Magnitude of δ_{geo} is equal to the area Ω of the portion of the sphere enclosed by the great circles. We can check the result in several ways. The following formula gives the are of the spherical triangle:

$$\Omega = 2 \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{\mathbf{r}_A \cdot \mathbf{r}_B \times \mathbf{r}_C}{1 + \mathbf{r}_A \cdot \mathbf{r}_B + \mathbf{r}_B \cdot \mathbf{r}_C + \mathbf{r}_C \cdot \mathbf{r}_A} \right] \quad (17)$$

In this example

$$\mathbf{r}_A = \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{3}/2 \\ 0 \\ 1/2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{r}_B = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \sqrt{3}/2 \\ 1/2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{r}_C = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (18)$$

Geometric phase as a sum of phases acquired in open paths

Let A and B be two points on the sphere. φ_A and φ_B are the initial and final states corresponding to the points A and B . Let \mathbf{O}_{AB} be an unitary (or hermitian) operator that rotates (or projects) φ_A to φ_B . $\mathbf{O}_{AB}\varphi_A$ differs from φ_B by a phase [6]:

$$\mathbf{O}_{AB}\varphi_A = e^{i\delta_{AB}}\varphi_B, \quad \text{where} \quad e^{i\delta_{AB}} = \varphi_B^\dagger \mathbf{O}_{AB}\varphi_A \quad (19)$$

As an example consider the path $A \rightarrow B$ in Figure 3 and omit the normalization factors

$$\mathbf{O}_{AB}\varphi_A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -\frac{i}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}i}{2} \\ \frac{i}{2} & \frac{1}{4} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{4} \\ -\frac{\sqrt{3}i}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{4} & \frac{3}{4} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} \\ -i \\ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 + \frac{3i}{4} \\ -\frac{i}{2} - \frac{3}{8} \\ \frac{\sqrt{3}i}{2} + \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{8} \end{pmatrix} \quad (20)$$

$$\varphi_B^\dagger \mathbf{O}_{AB}\varphi_A = \frac{3}{2} + 2i \quad \rightarrow \quad \tan \delta_{AB} = \frac{4}{3} \quad \text{or} \quad \delta_{AB} = +53.13^\circ \quad (21)$$

Similarly we find $\delta_{BC} = -90^\circ$ and $\delta_{CA} = 0$. There is no dynamical phase with projection operators, hence

$$\delta_{geo} = \delta_{total} = \delta_{AB} + \delta_{BC} + \delta_{CA} = +53.13^\circ - 90^\circ + 0^\circ = -36.87^\circ \quad \text{as found before.} \quad (22)$$

Weyl equations in 3-d

Eigenvectors φ_\pm of $\boldsymbol{\Sigma} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}$ corresponding to the eigenvalues ± 1 are 3-component complex valued vectors similar to the 2-component Weyl spinors and they are solutions to the 3-d Weyl equations:

$$(i\partial_t - \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \cdot \mathbf{p})\varphi = 0 \quad (23)$$

$$(i\partial_t + \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \cdot \mathbf{p})\varphi = 0 \quad (24)$$

where $\mathbf{p} = |\mathbf{p}|\hat{\mathbf{n}}$. Plane wave ansatz suggest that φ_+ and φ_- that given in Eq.(3) are the solutions associated with right- and left-helicity states. These equations can also be written as

$$(g^0\partial_0 + g^i\partial_i)\varphi = 0 \quad (25)$$

$$(g^0\partial_0 - g^i\partial_i)\varphi = 0 \quad (26)$$

where $g^0 = I_{3\times 3}$, $g^i = iS^i$. It can be shown that 3-d Weyl equations are Lorentz covariant under rotations.

Lorentz covariance of 3-d Weyl equations

Following the procedure given by Bjorken and Drell [9], Lorentz covariance of Eq.(25) under the rotations is satisfied if a matrix R exists such that:

$$(R^{-1})^\dagger g^\mu R^{-1} = \Lambda^\mu_\nu g^\nu \quad (27)$$

where $g^0 = I_{3\times 3}$, $g^i = iS^i$ and

$$\Lambda = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & R(\mathbf{n}, \alpha) \end{pmatrix} \quad (28)$$

It can be shown that the matrix $R(\mathbf{n}, \alpha)$ given in Eq.(4) is the desired matrix, and Eq.(27) is satisfied.

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